

Inhibition effect of glycine derivatives on corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution

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Abstract : The inhibition effect of glycine (1), *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (2), *N*-benzoyl glycine (3), *N*-benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazole (4) and *N*-benzoylmethylbenzimidazole (5) towards the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution has been studied using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order $1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5$. The inhibition efficiency of 5 with 4×10^{-5} M concentration is the highest, which reaches 90.3–94.4%. It has been observed that introduction of benzene ring increases the inhibition efficiency of glycine by 18–57% and on converting the carboxyl group into benzimidazole group; the inhibition efficiency is further increased by 8–43%.

Keywords : Glycine, polarization, impedance, brass, benzimidazole, corrosion inhibition.

Introduction

Copper and its alloy are extensively used to fabricate structures and components exposed to sea water and other marine environments¹. Moreover, hydrochloric acid is extensively used for removal of rust and scale in several industrial processes. The use of inhibitor is one of the most practical methods to protect metals and alloys from corrosion, especially in aggressive environments². Benzotriazole and its derivatives offer a good protection against corrosion of brass in aggressive environments, viz. 3–3.5% NaCl solutions and sea water^{3,4}. But these compounds are toxic⁵. Now, the research area is oriented to the development of green corrosion inhibitors and some researchers investigated the inhibition effect of amino acids on metal corrosion^{5–15}. Recently inhibition effect of various amino acids on copper and steel corrosion in HCl solution has been studied^{5,16–18}.

Looking for environmentally acceptable corrosion inhibitors for brass in marine environment, we have chosen glycine (1) as starting materials and prepared *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (2), *N*-benzoyl glycine (3), 2-benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazole (4), 2-benzamidomethylbenzimidazole (5). Two electrochemical techniques potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy have been used to study the effect of the addition of these compounds on the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The chemical composition of the commercial brass used in the present study was 59.8% Cu, 40.0% Zn and traces of Fe and Pb. The working electrode for potentiodynamic study and EIS measurement was prepared from the brass rod from which only the circular cross section (0.25 cm²) of rod was exposed. The brass sample was polished successively with

- (a) belt grinding polishing machine,
- (b) metallographic emery paper of increasing fineness of up to 1200 grade and
- (c) cloth polishing by Single Disc Polishing Machine CENSICO PMV-T 10-1.

Then the samples were degreased with AR grade ethanol and acetone and rinsed with double distilled water prior to each experiment.

Glycine was AR grade reagent and used as received. The ligands 2, 3, 4 and 5 were prepared by following usual procedure described in our earlier communication^{19,20}. Fig. 1 shows the molecular structure of the investigated compounds and their inhibition efficiency. Analytical data of the derivatives are given in Table 1. The pH measurements were made with an Orion 420A Plus pH meter using 9157BN Triode pH electrode. The

Structure of the compds	Inhibition efficiency (%)		
	Tafel extrapolation method	EIS method	Average
 1	22.6	32.0	27.3
 2	41.6	49.7	45.6
 3	81.0	88.3	84.6
 4	86.3	92.2	89.2
 5	90.3	94.4	92.3

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the inhibitors and their inhibition efficiency

Table 1. Analytical data of the inhibitors

Inhibitors	% Yield (m p °C)	Eq wt Found (Calcd)	Analysis (%)			pK* values
			Obsd (Calcd)			
			C	H	N	
2	80	214.9	-	-	6.43	4.60
	(168)	(215.0)	-	-	(6.50)	(COOH)
3	80	178.9	-	-	7.94	4.95
	(186)	(179.0)	-	-	(7.82)	(COOH)
4	60	-	58.4	4.43	14.50	4.72
	(183)	-	(58.53)	(4.53)	(14.63)	(Benzimidazolium ion)
4	55	-	71.8	5.20	16.75	4.75
	(218)	-	(71.7)	(5.20)	(16.70)	(Benzimidazolium ion)

pH meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solution in water. Following solutions (50 ml) were titrated potentiometrically in water-acetone (1:1) at 30 ± 0.5 °C and $\mu = 0.25$ (NaClO₄) against 0.150 M NaOH solution, (a) 0.01 M HClO₄, (b) 0.01 M

HClO₄ + 0.02 M 2 or 3 or 4H⁺ or 5H⁺, (c) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.03 M 2 or 3 or 4H⁺ or 5H⁺. The aggressive environment used was 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution prepared from AR grade reagent and double distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0. Oxygen con-

tent of the sodium chloride solution was 7.3 mg/L. All other reagents were of AR quality. THERMO-NORHAN-USA Model SIX-NSS-200 was used to record EDS data.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out with polished and degreased brass specimens having an exposed surface area of 0.25 cm². The electrochemical measurements were carried out in a standard three-electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml. The counter electrode was a platinum plate with 1 cm² surface area, the reference electrode consisted of a commercial saturated calomel electrode with a Luggin capillary bridge and the working electrode was made up of brass. Polarization studies were carried out using potentiostat/galvanostat (ACM Instruments Gill AC) and the data obtained were analyzed using the software "ACM Instruments version 5". The degreased working electrode was immersed in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution and allowed to stabilize for 30 min²¹. The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass specimen in the test solution with and without inhibitors were recorded at a scan rate of 1 mV/s in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution (pH 6) at 30 ± 0.5 °C. The inhibition efficiencies of the compounds were determined from corrosion current density using the Tafel extrapolation method.

Electrochemical AC impedance studies :

AC impedance measurements were conducted at room temperature using "ACM Instruments Gill AC". The instruments were controlled by the software "ACM Instruments version 5" between 1m Hz and 100 kHz. An AC sinusoid voltage of ~ ± 10 mV was applied at corrosion potential (E_{corr}). The brass sample with an exposing surface area of 0.25 cm² was used as the working electrode. A three electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml with a platinum plate electrode and a saturated calomel electrode was used²².

Results and discussion

The ability of an organic molecule to inhibit metal corrosion depends on several factors and some of them are the shape, aromaticity, bond strength to metal substrate, the presence of heteroatom and number of bonding atoms or groups²³⁻²⁶. Temperature, pH and stability

in the aggressive media are also factors related to the efficiency of the inhibitor²⁷⁻³². All compounds are stable in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution, room temperature 30 ± 0.5 °C was selected for inhibition studies. Experiments carried out at pH 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 using inhibitor II by weight loss method. It has been observed that inhibition efficiency is maximum in between pH 6 to 8 and pH 6 is selected for these studies. Concentration of chloride ion in sea water is 0.54. Hence 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution is chosen.

Glycine is good inhibitor in HCl and H₂SO₄ solution¹⁸. But at pH 6 inhibition efficiency of glycine is only 22-32%. After introducing C₆H₅SO₂- group inhibition efficiency is increased by 20%. On introduction of C₆H₅CO- group inhibition efficiency is increased by 50%. This is due to the presence of π-electron of the benzene ring. Compound 3 is better inhibitor than 2 due to more basic character and presence of planar carboxyl group. The carboxyl group is converted to benzimidazole group to improve further its inhibition efficiency. The inhibiting efficiency of 4 and 5 is higher than 85% and the inhibiting efficiency of 5 with a concentration of 0.04 mM is the highest at room temperature, which reaches 90-94.4%.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution with varying concentrations (10⁻⁴ to 10⁻⁶ M) of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were recorded and are shown in the Figs. 2-6. The potentiodynamic polarization parameters are listed in Table 2. Inhibition efficiencies³³ are calculated using the following equation :

Inhibition efficiency = $[I_{\text{corr}} - I_{\text{corr (inh)}}/I_{\text{corr}}] \times 100$
where $I_{\text{corr (inh)}}$ and I_{corr} are the corrosion current density value with and without inhibitor, respectively.

All reagents show relatively same behaviour against the polarization. Moreover, these inhibitors do not change the profile of the anodic and cathodic curves, indicating that the inhibitors merely block the reaction sites of metal surface without affecting the anodic and cathodic reaction mechanism. With increasing inhibitor concentration, no obvious trend is observed in the shift of E_{corr} values suggesting that these compounds behave as mixed type inhibitors.

Fig. 2. Effect of 1 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 3. Effect of 2 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 4. Effect of 3 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 5. Effect of 4 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 6. Effect of 5 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Table 2. The electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency values for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	E_{corr} (mV) vs SCE	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	I.E. (%)
	0	-301.8	6.14	
1	4×10^{-4}	-286.8	4.89	20.3
1	4×10^{-5}	-236.7	4.75	22.6
1	4×10^{-6}	-256.2	5.28	14.0
2	4×10^{-4}	-253.6	3.64	40.7
2	4×10^{-5}	-249.5	3.58	41.6
2	4×10^{-6}	-234.5	3.78	38.4
3	4×10^{-4}	-238.7	1.50	75.5
3	4×10^{-5}	-229.3	1.14	81.4
3	4×10^{-6}	-235.4	1.82	70.3
4	4×10^{-4}	-243.5	1.17	80.9
4	4×10^{-5}	-228.9	0.84	86.3
4	4×10^{-6}	-233.3	1.83	70.1
5	4×10^{-4}	-223.7	0.88	85.6
5	4×10^{-5}	-227.4	0.59	90.3
5	4×10^{-6}	-243.9	1.01	83.5

Electrochemical AC impedance studies :

The effects of varying concentrations (10^{-4} to 10^{-6} M) of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 on the impedance behaviour of brass in

0.6 M NaCl solution were obtained and are depicted in the Figs. 7–11. These curves show Nyquist plots of brass in presence of inhibitors and in absence of inhibitors. These plots reveal that the impedance response of the brass has significantly changed after using these inhibitors. Various impedance parameters such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) and inhibition efficiency (IE) are given in Table 3. The charge transfer values are calculated from the difference in impedance at lower and higher frequencies as suggested by Haruyama *et al.*³⁴. The percentage efficiency of corrosion of brass is calculated from R_{ct} as follows³⁵ :

$$IE = [R_{ct}^{-1} - R_{ct(inh)}^{-1}/R_{ct}^{-1}] \times 100$$

where $R_{ct(inh)}$ and R_{ct} are charge transfer resistance values with and without inhibitor respectively. The trend of increase in inhibition efficiency is same as in polarization study i.e. there is a good agreement between the results obtained from polarization and impedance studies (Tables 2–3).

EDS data indicated the presence of chlorine, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen on the surface of the alloy indicating film formation.

Fig. 7. Effect of 1 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 8. Effect of 2 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 9. Effect of 3 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 10. Effect of 4 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 11. Effect of 5 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Table 3. The impedance measurements and inhibition efficiency values of sulphonamido derivatives for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	R_{ct} (K ohm)	C_{dl} (F)	I.E. (R_{ct}) %
	0	0.358	2.38×10^{-4}	
1	4×10^{-4}	0.510	2.65×10^{-4}	29.8
1	4×10^{-5}	0.527	9.39×10^{-4}	32.0
1	4×10^{-6}	0.435	1.95×10^{-4}	17.7
2	4×10^{-4}	0.668	3.07×10^{-4}	46.1
2	4×10^{-5}	0.713	1.45×10^{-4}	49.7
2	4×10^{-6}	0.669	1.32×10^{-4}	46.4
3	4×10^{-4}	1.762	1.55×10^{-4}	79.6
3	4×10^{-5}	3.069	1.02×10^{-4}	88.3
3	4×10^{-6}	1.490	1.63×10^{-4}	75.9
4	4×10^{-4}	2.342	1.63×10^{-4}	84.7
4	4×10^{-5}	3.571	5.63×10^{-5}	89.9
4	4×10^{-6}	1.490	1.63×10^{-4}	75.9
5	4×10^{-4}	3.545	5.72×10^{-5}	89.9
5	4×10^{-5}	6.445	1.24×10^{-4}	94.4
5	4×10^{-6}	3.203	3.42×10^{-5}	88.8

The inhibition efficiency of glycine is in the range of 23–32%. It is increased by 19–56% after introduction of

C_6H_5- group (2 and 3). The inhibition efficiency is further improved (86.0–94%) by converting $-COOH$ groups to benzimidazole groups.

Conclusion :

From the results of the study the following conclusions can be drawn :

(i) All investigated glycine derivatives have shown inhibiting properties for brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution.

(ii) The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the compounds increases in the following order $1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5$.

(iii) Significant improvement in the inhibition property of the glycine is observed by introducing C_6H_5- group. Further improvement is achieved when carboxyl group is converted to benzimidazole group.

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